

STRUCTURAL AND SEMANTIC ANALYSIS OF PAREMIOLOGICAL UNITS IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES: A COMPARATIVE STUDY BASED ON DICTIONARY MATERIALS

Ruzikulov E.Sh.

Teacher, Department of Foreign Languages, Samarkand State University of Architecture and
Construction

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14253373>

Abstract. *The study titled "Structural and Semantic Analysis of Paremiological Units in English and Uzbek Languages: A Comparative Study Based on Dictionary Materials" explores the role of proverbs and similar sayings (paremiological units) in both English and Uzbek languages. Paremiology, the study of proverbs, aphorisms, and wise sayings, plays a crucial role in understanding the cultural, social, and linguistic features of a society. Proverbs encapsulate the collective wisdom of a community, reflecting its values, beliefs, and daily experiences.*

Keywords: *paremiological Units, Structurizer, Semantic analysis, Cultural reflection, Cross-linguistic comparison, Comparative study, linguistic elements, different languages.*

Paremiology, derived from the Greek words “paroimia” (proverb) and “logos” (study or discourse), is the scholarly investigation of proverbs, their meanings, and their functions within various cultures. This fascinating branch of folklore and linguistics delves into the role that proverbs, aphorisms, and wise sayings play in shaping collective wisdom, societal norms, and everyday communication.

Paremiology, the study of proverbs, is a fascinating field within linguistics and folklore that explores the role of short, traditional sayings in human communication. Derived from the Greek terms *paroimia* (proverb) and *logos* (study), paremiology seeks to understand how proverbs shape culture, convey wisdom, and offer insights into social norms and behaviors. Across the world, proverbs have been passed down through generations, reflecting cultural values, human experiences, and collective wisdom. By studying them, paremiologists explore not only language but also the cultural frameworks within which these sayings develop.

This article provides an overview of paremiology, focusing on key terms, research methods, and concluding with the importance of this field in understanding both cultural and linguistic dynamics.

This research aims to compare the structural and semantic aspects of paremiological units in English and Uzbek, utilizing dictionary materials as the primary data source. It examines how proverbs in each language differ in form, meaning, and usage, while also identifying common themes and linguistic features that are shared across both cultures. The study focuses on how language structure, metaphorical expressions, and cultural context shape the interpretation and function of proverbs in both languages.

Through this comparative analysis, the study seeks to highlight not only the linguistic differences and similarities between English and Uzbek proverbs but also the cultural insights that these sayings provide into the societies in which they are used. The findings aim to contribute to

the broader field of paremiology and cross-cultural communication, shedding light on the universal and culturally specific aspects of wisdom embedded in language.

Paremiology, the study of proverbs, reveals a wealth of cultural and linguistic insights. Proverbs, or paremiological units, serve as reflections of societal values, encapsulating universal truths or practical wisdom. By examining proverbs in different languages, we can better understand not only linguistic structures but also the cultural narratives they represent. This article explores the structural and semantic analysis of paremiological units in both English and Uzbek languages, using dictionary materials as the primary source for data collection. A comparative approach is employed to uncover differences and similarities in the structure and meaning of proverbs across these two languages, thereby shedding light on how cultural context shapes their formulation and interpretation.

The study of paremiological units – proverbs and sayings – offers a valuable lens into the cultural and linguistic richness of any language. In both English and Uzbek languages, proverbs encapsulate moral lessons, cultural norms, and societal wisdom that have been passed down through generations. However, understanding the structure and semantics of these proverbs requires a deep analysis of their linguistic composition and the meanings they convey.

This article aims to explore the structure and semantic analysis of paremiological units in English and Uzbek languages, using dictionary materials as the primary source of data. By comparing the structural patterns and meanings in both languages, the study highlights how cultural context shapes the formation and interpretation of proverbs.

Though the study of proverbs has ancient roots, with notable mentions in the works of Aristotle and other classical philosophers, paremiology as a formal discipline began to take shape in the late 19th and early 20th centuries. Scholars recognized that proverbs are not only short, pithy expressions of truth or advice but also reflections of the cultural and historical contexts from which they arise.

Proverbs have long served as carriers of wisdom, often passed down orally from one generation to the next. They provide a snapshot of how a society views the world, addressing issues such as morality, human behavior, and relationships. The universality of proverbs across languages and cultures suggests that humanity shares common experiences, yet each culture also adapts these sayings to fit its unique values and worldview.

In every culture, proverbs serve multiple purposes:

Communication of Common Wisdom: Proverbs distill complex ideas into simple, memorable phrases. They are often used in everyday speech to convey practical advice or warnings, such as English proverb “A stitch in time saves nine”, which encourages timely action to prevent bigger problems later.

Cultural Identity and Continuity: Proverbs help reinforce cultural traditions and values. By using them, people affirm their belonging to a particular community, passing down the collective wisdom from elders to younger generations.

Conflict Resolution and Persuasion: Proverbs are often invoked in arguments or negotiations to make a point or validate a position. The authority of a proverb can strengthen an argument by appealing to widely accepted truths, for example, “Don’t count your chickens before they hatch” and advises caution when faced with uncertainty.

Moral Guidance: Many proverbs address ethical concerns, teaching right from wrong. The African proverb “It takes a village to raise a child” emphasizes the communal responsibility in

nurturing the next generation, while the Chinese saying “Give a man a fish, and you feed him for a day; teach a man to fish, and you feed him for a lifetime” highlights the importance of self-reliance and education.

Cross-Cultural Insights in Paremiology: One of the most intriguing aspects of paremiology is the discovery of similar proverbs in vastly different cultures. For instance, the concept of not rushing into things is echoed in the Spanish proverb “No dejes para mañana lo que puedes hacer hoy” (Don’t leave for tomorrow what you can do today) and the Russian saying “Завтра никогда не наступит” (Tomorrow never comes).

These parallels suggest that human societies, despite their differences, experience life in comparable ways. However, there are also distinct variations that reveal unique cultural attitudes. For example, while Western cultures may emphasize individualism in sayings like “The early bird catches the worm”, which rewards personal initiative, some Eastern proverbs focus on harmony and collective well-being, such as the Japanese proverb “出る杭は打たれる” (The nail that sticks out gets hammered down), which discourages drawing attention to oneself.

Paremiology has become an interdisciplinary field, combining elements of anthropology, sociology, and linguistics. Researchers use proverbs to analyze not only language but also social structures, ideologies, and power dynamics within a society. Moreover, the advent of globalization and digital communication has led to the evolution of new proverbs and aphorisms, especially in online communities.

For instance, internet culture has spawned modern proverbs such as “Don’t feed the trolls”, advising users not to engage with disruptive online behavior, while memes and hashtags often encapsulate modern-day wisdom, offering a new frontier for paremiologists to explore.

The first stage of analysis involves collecting a set of proverbs from authoritative dictionary sources. For English proverbs, sources like The Oxford Dictionary of English Proverbs provide a comprehensive repository of traditional sayings, while for Uzbek, works such as O‘zbek xalq maqollari (Uzbek Folk Proverbs) are referenced. Proverbs from both languages are grouped into thematic categories, such as family, morality, time, and work, to facilitate direct comparison.

The structurizer method focuses on the syntactic structure of proverbs both in English and Uzbek languages. English proverbs typically follow a Subject-Verb-Object (SVO) structure, whereas Uzbek proverbs follow a Subject-Object-Verb (SOV) structure, reflecting the syntactic norms of Turkic languages.

English Example: “*Actions speak louder than words*” (SVO).

Uzbek Example: “*Ko‘p gap – bekor ish*” (Too many words – wasted effort) (SOV).

This structural analysis highlights how English proverbs tend to present ideas in a linear, direct fashion, while Uzbek proverbs often build up toward the action (verb), reflecting a different narrative structure. Identifying these patterns provides insight into how different cultures prioritize elements in speech. In this phase, we analyze the meanings and cultural implications of the collected proverbs. English proverbs often utilize metaphorical language grounded in a more urbanized, industrial context, such as “Don’t cry over spilled milk” (regret over small, irreversible mistakes). Uzbek proverbs, in contrast, frequently draw from agricultural and pastoral imagery, reflecting the country’s agrarian roots. For instance, “Erning tuzi – ayol” (A man’s salt is his wife) emphasizes family roles and social harmony in Uzbek culture.

Through semantic analysis, we also compare figurative language in both languages. While English proverbs might emphasize individualism and practicality, Uzbek proverbs often stress

communal values, patience, and resilience, such as “Sabr – oltin kalit” (Patience is a golden key), promoting the virtue of endurance and perseverance. Proverbs serve as reflections of a culture’s core values, attitudes, and beliefs. By analyzing proverbs within their cultural context, we see how English proverbs often focus on efficiency, pragmatism, and individualism, as in “Time is money”. In contrast, Uzbek proverbs like “Mehnatning tagi rohat” (The root of labor is comfort) reveal an emphasis on patience, hard work, and long-term rewards. The pragmatic function of proverbs in everyday language use also differs between cultures. In English, proverbs are often used to offer advice or settle disputes with concise wisdom. In Uzbek culture, proverbs frequently reinforce social norms, serving as reminders of expected behavior in familial and community contexts.

Paremiology is more than the study of quaint, old sayings; it is a window into the soul of cultures and societies. Proverbs, though short and often simple in structure, carry profound meaning, shaping human interaction and preserving centuries of wisdom. As societies evolve, so too do their proverbs, continuing to serve as markers of identity, tools of education, and vehicles for shared understanding.

The structural and semantic analysis of paremiological units in English and Uzbek languages offer important insights into the interplay between language, culture, and social values. Structurally, English proverbs tend to follow a more linear, SVO format, while Uzbek proverbs reflect an SOV structure that builds meaning toward the verb. Semantically, both languages utilize metaphors, but the cultural imagery they draw from is distinct, with English proverbs reflecting urbanized, individualist tendencies and Uzbek proverbs emphasizing agrarian values and social harmony. Paremiology offers profound insights into the way language reflects culture, transmits wisdom, and navigates social interaction. Through methods such as textual analysis, oral history, and comparative studies, researchers uncover the layers of meaning embedded in proverbs and their significance in human communication. In a globalized world where cultures increasingly interact, paremiology helps reveal both the commonality of human experience and the uniqueness of cultural expression.

As the study of proverbs continues to expand, it will provide valuable perspectives on how societies communicate core values and how language evolves to adapt to changing contexts. Proverbial wisdom, though simple in form, remains a powerful tool for understanding the complexities of human behavior across time and space.

REFERENCES

1. Mirziyoyev Sh.M. from his speech at the meeting at Nagoya University in Japan.
2. Ruzikulov E.Sh. “Paremiology as a studyobject of phraseology” Science and Innovationn International scientific journal volume 2 issue 3 march 2023 uif-2022: 8.2 | issn: 2181-3337 | scientists.uz p 29.
3. Larin B.A. Essay on phraseology // Essay on lexicology, phraseology and stylistics: Three. zap. /LGU. - L., 1956. - No. 198. - P. 201-202.
4. Vinogradov V.V. Basic concepts of Russian phraseology and linguistic dictcipliny. - L., 1946. - P.61
5. Abdumurotovich, Kuchiboev Mansur. "A Lingo-Poetic Analysis of Translations of Shakespeare's.
6. Smith, L. P. Phraseology of the English language. M. :Drofa, 1998, 158 p. - P. 34.